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Green Synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles using Neem Leaf Extract and their Characterization

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Abstract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles was synthesized by using (*Azadirachta Indica*) Neem leaf extract. In these different parts of neem tree such as leaves, bark, twigs and fruits are used for synthesis ZnO nanoparticles mainly by two methods: one by soaking and another by boiling. It also provides an unconventional and fresh approach which shows that it is a reliable, non-toxic in nature, eco-friendly and also low-cost method. The synthesized Zinc oxide nanoparticle was then characterized by using X-ray diffraction technique, Ultra violet (UV) and FTIR technique. The particle size was found to be 32 nm. It also exhibits the synthesized nanoparticle are in crystalline in nature. This method offers a biological technique to synthesize ZnO nanoparticles in controlled and precise manner with well-defined diverse sizes and shapes. Also, the band gap energy was found to be 4.5 eV. The green synthesized method can be used as an alternative to the existing chemical and physical methods.

Key Words: *Neem Leaf, Zinc Nitrate.*

1. Introduction

Over last few decades, nanotechnology has established as the great innovation in modern science and technology. Nanoparticle is well-defined as a small object that behaves as a whole part in terms of its transport and properties. (1). As Green synthesis of nanoparticle is an advanced and innovative branch of nanotechnology it has gained more significant importance and become one of the most useable methods (2). The biosynthesis method of plant extracts has drawn attention as a simple and viable substitute to chemical procedures and physical methods [3]. Zinc oxide, is a crystalline yellowish-white powder and is almost completely soluble in water. It shows hexagonal Wurtzite crystalline structure. The Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles is a type of inorganic compound and due to the unique physical, chemical, and biological properties it has widespread application as an additive in a wide variety of materials and products, including ceramics, glass, cement, and rubber, amongst others (4,5). *Azadirachta indica* commonly known as Neem belongs to *Meliaceae* family. Each part of the tree has been used as a traditional medicine for various household remedy. The major advantage of using the neem leaves is that it is a normally available medicinal plant and the biosynthesized ZnO nanoparticle might have been enhanced as it was capped with the neem leaf extract [6].

2. Experimental

Synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

Preparation of Neem Leaves (*Azadirachta Indica*) Extract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were synthesized from neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and leaf extracts using zinc nitrate ($Zn(NO_3)_2$) as the precursor. The leaves were washed with water to remove dirt and dust and dried. The leaves were then oven dried at 30 °C for 6-8 days. After

complete drying, the leaves were ground to powder using a mixer grinder by using moter pestel. The powder is then mixer grinder and add 250 ml of distilled water and stirred to obtained Neem leaf extract.

After that 150 ml neem leaf extracts were boiled on a hot water bath. when the leaf extract started boiling, 20 g zinc nitrate was added and stirred constantly. The mixture was boiled till paste was obtained. The paste was then transferred to silica crucible and heated at high temperature of 600 °C for one hours in a muffle furnace. A white colour Zinc oxide nanoparticles obtained.

Figure 3.1 : Preparation of Neem leaves (*Azadirachta Indica*) extract

3. Characterization

Zinc oxide nanoparticle was synthesized by using green synthesis method from zinc nitrate $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, using Neem (*Azadirachta Indica*) Leaf Extract. The obtained material was calcinated at 600 °c in muffle furnace.

3.1. X-ray diffraction analysis

Figure 3.2 : X Ray Diffraction

The XRD pattern of pristine zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticle synthesized by green synthesis method and calcinated at 600°C as shown in figure 4.1.(a).The crystalline nature with 2θ peak lying at (100), (002), (101), (102), (110) and (103) planes. All the peaks match well the standard hexagonal wurtzite structure of zinc oxide (ZnO) with lattice constants $a = b = 0.3249$ nm and $c = 0.5206$ nm [JCPDS card no. 36-1451]. All the peaks are perfectly match with pure ZnO structure, which indicates the high purity of the obtained ZnO nanoparticle. The average crystalline size was found to be 21 nm calculated by Deye-Scherrer formula [7].

3.2 Fourier Transform Infrared

The FTIR spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles is shown in Figure 3. The major peak for the Neem plant extract shifting from 3428.62 cm^{-1} ZnO was assigned to the O-H of the phenol groups and -NH_2 stretching vibrations. $837\text{-}805\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the aromatic compound (C-H) and stretching for the amine group C-N, C=C and N-H at the range of 1505 cm^{-1} . ZnO nanoparticles showed a sharp and intense at 433.04 cm^{-1} [8]

Figure 3.3 FTIR Spectroscopy of ZnO NPs

3.3 UV-Visible spectroscopy

UV-phototypesetter analysis was done for preliminary confirmation of green synthesized

nanoparticles. Absorbance peak of green synthesized ZnO NPs obtained in UV wavelength

range (200-375nm), which confirmed their size in nano range. ZnO NPs synthesized using Neem extract exhibited absorbance peaks at 272 nm.[9]

The band gap for the nanoparticle is calculated by the formula = $E = hc/\lambda$ calculated band gap value is 4.5 eV.

where,

E = band gap

h = Planck's

constant c =

velocity of the light

λ = wavelength

Figure 3.4. UV -Vis spectrum of ZnO NPs.

4. Conclusion

Zinc oxide nanoparticle was synthesised by a simple, efficient, cheap, environment-friendly and green protocol by using $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with neem (*Azadirachta Indica*) Leaf extract. The material was characterised by using X Ray diffraction method and particle size was found to be 21 nm. The synthesis of ZnO NP was measured using the UV- Visible spectroscopy at a maximum absorbance of 272 nm. The FTIR analysis shows the presence of some reducing biomolecules associated with some organic functional (O=H) groups responsible for the encapsulation and stabilization of the NPs. The band gap of prepared ZnO nanoparticle is found to be 4.5 eV.

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